

The AlphaFold educational summit provides insights into advancing global equity in computational structural biology

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Abstract

AlphaFold is a state-of-the-art protein structure prediction resource that offers immense potential for accelerating scientific discovery. Realising this potential, however, requires equitable access to technology, resources and expertise. To address this need, the AlphaFold Education Summit, held at the Wellcome Genome Campus in Hinxton, Cambridge, UK, convened researchers and trainers from 14 countries, with a focus on low- and middle-income countries (LMICs).

Participants, selected for their AlphaFold expertise and training experience, shared crucial insights into dissemination strategies. Over a four-day train-the-trainer programme, participants advanced their AlphaFold knowledge, formulated adaptable training models, and collectively committed to facilitating the widespread application of AlphaFold in scientific exploration.

This report details the summit's objectives, key discussions, and outcomes, charting a course towards a sustainable and inclusive global AlphaFold community. Major barriers identified include limited computational infrastructure, inconsistent internet connectivity, and a shortage of skilled trainers in under-resourced regions. The summit underscored the importance of developing adaptable, high-quality training materials, implementing robust Train-the-Trainer (TtT) programmes, and fostering mentorship and community networks. Key strategic recommendations include collaborative resource sharing, sustainable funding models, integration of AlphaFold training into academic curricula, and establishing a global-south community with regional hubs to mitigate geopolitical and logistical challenges.

The summit outcomes emphasise the necessity of a coordinated, community-driven approach to democratise access to AI-powered structural biology tools. This approach focuses on inclusivity, sustainability, and long-term capacity building, aiming to empower researchers globally, accelerate scientific discovery, and ensure the benefits of new AI methods, like AlphaFold, are accessible across diverse scientific and geographical contexts.

Introduction

Proteins, the workhorses of cellular machinery, underpin virtually all biological processes. Understanding their three-dimensional structure is pivotal for elucidating their functions and mechanisms, driving advancements in fields ranging from drug discovery to agricultural biotechnology (1–3). Historically, determining protein structures has been challenging, requiring resource-intensive experimental techniques such as X-ray crystallography, Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR), and cryo-electron microscopy (Cryo-EM), coupled with specialised expertise and substantial computational power (4,5). The complexity and cost of experimental protein structure determination created significant barriers, particularly for researchers with limited resources, leading to a global inequity in accessing structural insights from experimentally derived protein structure models relevant to the global South. While theoretical approaches have progressed, homology/comparative modelling remains constrained by its reliance on the availability of templates with significant similarity to the target protein in structural databases. The rate of novel protein folds has slowed considerably, suggesting a convergence to a few thousand folds. However, the potential of homology-based methods to predict new structures of proteins with low sequence identity with the ones available at the PDB is still challenging.

The recent resurgence of artificial intelligence (AI), following decades of development and advances in machine learning and deep learning algorithms, has introduced strategies for optimising and analysing biomolecular structures. The advent of AlphaFold 2, a state-of-the-art deep learning algorithm, revolutionised the landscape by enabling near-accurate protein structure prediction directly from amino acid sequences (6). This breakthrough led to the establishment of the AlphaFold Protein Structure Database (AlphaFold DB), democratising access to structural models by providing researchers worldwide free access to over 200 million high-accuracy protein structure predictions. The AlphaFold DB equips scientists, regardless of local access to sophisticated experimental or computational infrastructure, to explore the structures of proteins relevant to their research. The subsequent release of the AlphaFold Server further

accelerated prediction timescales, providing web-based structural prediction capabilities for non-commercial research with a stable internet connection.

Predicted models from AlphaFold have proved to be an exceptional tool to bridge fundamental protein research with breakthroughs in all fields of biology (2), including personalised medicine, biotechnology and environmental applications. For example, researchers have leveraged AlphaFold to guide the development of a modified inhibitor protein that specifically targets pectin methylesterases secreted from pathogens (7). This modified inhibitor enhanced plant resistance to oomycete and fungal pathogens, demonstrating AI-driven protein structure modelling's potential to accelerate the development of new strategies for plant protection. Furthermore, the AlphaFold DB has facilitated the discovery of novel enzymes with industrial applications, such as a new polyethylene terephthalate (PET) hydrolase with enhanced PET-degrading capabilities, showcasing AlphaFold's utility in addressing environmental challenges such as plastic pollution (8).

Although access to AlphaFold has transformed life science research, analyses conducted by Google DeepMind on AlphaFold citation data using OpenAlex, an open scientometric database (9), revealed a notable adoption gap among scientists from lower-middle- and low-income countries when compared with structural biology citation baselines. For example, these countries participated in just over 5% of publications citing studies in the AlphaFold corpus compared with approximately 14% of structural biology publications (and around 50% of the global population)¹. This suggests that, despite AlphaFold's global scientific impact, access to AI-driven tools and research opportunities remains limited in resource-constrained settings. The mere availability of AlphaFold or predicted structures through the AlphaFold Database does not guarantee effective application. This disparity is attributed to key factors identified through scientists' interviews, notably limited access to computational and research infrastructure as well as gaps in relevant skills and expertise. We conclude that bioscientific communities in low-resource settings, including but not limited to those in the global south, would benefit from integration of advanced biodata science

¹ The AlphaFold corpus includes the AlphaFold 2 and AlphaFold 3 methods paper, the AlphaFold Protein Structure Database papers, and the AlphaFold Multimer paper.

technologies such as AlphaFold into their research; to achieve this, they require both infrastructure and training. In this sense, challenges in adapting AlphaFold for context-specific biological research, such as in disease modelling, agricultural studies, and drug-target interaction mapping, further contribute to the limited application in under-resourced regions.

Capacity-building initiatives have proved instrumental in strengthening the research environment across Africa. Long-running projects such as H3ABioNet (10), DSI-Africa (11), and AfriGen-D have played a pivotal role in building a robust community focused on delivering high-quality computational analyses and training in bioinformatics and computational biology. Initiatives with a stronger focus on computational structural biology, such as BioStruct-Africa (www.biostructafrica.org/), illustrate why building local capacity is crucial for overcoming these challenges. For example, structural biology is an essential component of biomedical research in Africa, yet its development is hindered by limited access to infrastructure, training, and computational resources (12).

BioStruct-Africa's workshops, mentorship programmes, and computational structural biology training demonstrate a growing commitment to empowering African scientists to address these challenges. Beyond methodological limitations, another major challenge lies in the insufficient implementation and coordination of multidisciplinary research resources that integrate computational structural biology analysis to address biologically relevant problems in the African context.

Other initiatives, such as the Global Bioinformatics Education Summit (www.bioinfoedsummit.org/) and workshops hosted by the International Society for Computational Biology (ISCB, www.iscb.org), have demonstrated the value of bringing together researchers and educators to share best practices and develop training resources. Notably, the CABANA project (Capacity building for bioinformatics in Latin America) (13) and its follow-on project, CABANAnet (cabana.network/), provide a compelling model for regional capacity strengthening. Funded by the UK's Global Challenges Research Fund, CABANA invested in data analysis workshops, train-the-trainer programmes, and secondments across 10 Latin American countries, focusing on communicable diseases, sustainable food production, and biodiversity. Over

five years, this initiative trained over 800 individuals and demonstrated the impact of targeted training programmes. CABANAnet has continued and broadened this approach with funding from the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative and, importantly, is now led from Latin America. The project's success highlights the potential for similar initiatives to foster local expertise and address specific research needs. For example, the BiotrAI project (www.ebi.ac.uk/training/our-partnerships/biotrain), another collaboration supported by the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative and led by the EMBL–EBI and CABANAnet, aims to provide an integrated and up-to-date perspective on AI applications in the life sciences. This initiative includes modules on machine learning, deep learning, and AlphaFold, as well as training sessions covering both practical use and ethical implications of AI in the biosciences. In Mexico, national efforts have also contributed to building bioinformatics capacity. The Iberoamerican Society for Bioinformatics (www.soibio.org/), the Mexican Network for Bioinformatics (www.redmexicanadebioinformatica.org/), the National Bioinformatics Node (www.nnb.unam.mx/), and the Bioinformatics Software Developers Community (github.com/comunidadBioInfo) regularly organise training workshops and participate in international events. These initiatives play a key role in disseminating knowledge through open courses, thus helping democratise access to bioinformatics training.

The experiences above indicate that realising AlphaFold's full potential requires researchers to possess the knowledge and skills to generate, analyse and interpret and apply data, and apply their conclusions to the solution of biological and biomedical problems. This knowledge gap in structural data interpretation extends beyond geographical or resource limitations, additionally encompassing domain knowledge. The use of predicted macromolecular structures has the potential to facilitate research into diverse fields including neglected tropical diseases, bioengineering, drug discovery, and environmental science; disciplines often prominent in limited-resource research communities (e.g., rice genomics, local disease vector studies) (14). Thus, the need for targeted training becomes even more critical.

Recognising the urgent need to bridge this knowledge gap and foster a sustainable and inclusive global network for realising the transformative impact of AlphaFold, the AlphaFold Education Summit brought together researchers and educators from 14

countries at EMBL–EBI, Wellcome Genome Campus, UK. The summit examined the challenges and opportunities associated with integrating AlphaFold into scientific research and education, with a special focus on low–resource settings.

Summit objectives

The AlphaFold Education Summit was a collaborative initiative designed to empower researchers and educators globally to fully harness the potential of AlphaFold. This event provided a platform to understand the barriers to integrating AlphaFold into scientific research and education, with particular emphasis on the unique needs and limitations faced by educators and researchers in under–resourced regions. The summit aimed to enhance accessibility and practical application in diverse contexts.

Drawing on lessons from the CABANAnet and BioStruct–Africa initiatives (12,13), particularly in capacity building, regional ownership, and mentorship, researchers from under–resourced regions were central to shaping sustainable and scalable education strategies that are inclusive, effective, and contextually relevant at local and regional levels.

The summit's objectives were: (1) to provide access to bespoke training and resources to facilitate use of AlphaFold for relevant research in LMICs; (2) to equip researchers and educators to deliver training and build local capacity in under–resourced regions for the use and application of AlphaFold to their research; (3) to identify key challenges and develop mitigation strategies to build global capacity to fully exploit AlphaFold's potential in addressing local and global challenges; and (4) to foster collaboration and establish a sustainable, inclusive and active global community of AlphaFold users and trainers.

A central objective of the summit was the development of sustainable training programmes, with a strong focus on Train–the–Trainer (TtT) initiatives. These programmes are known to cultivate an active global community of trainers, fostering collaboration, mentorship, and knowledge exchange among educators and researchers

(15). The TtT programme at the summit was specifically designed to empower local experts to deliver high-quality AlphaFold training tailored to regional needs, ensuring effective and sustainable knowledge and skill dissemination. The summit also aimed to nucleate a global network of AlphaFold trainers to strengthen expertise in computational structural bioinformatics and computational biology, particularly in underserved regions. These efforts lay the groundwork for long-term impact, enabling future expansion of the field across regions. These training efforts also aimed to support region-specific scientific priorities, enabling participants to align AlphaFold applications with locally relevant research questions in health, agriculture, and environmental studies.

In addition to training, the summit facilitated workshops to explore practical applications of AlphaFold across diverse fields, from drug discovery and disease understanding to agricultural innovation and environmental science (7,8), demonstrating the versatility of structural predictions in addressing real-world problems. These workshops provided hands-on experience with the AlphaFold ecosystem and highlighted the importance of interdisciplinary understanding and collaboration in maximising the impact of predicted protein structures.

Finally, the summit served as a platform for discussing long-term strategies for lowering barriers and supporting equitable access and adoption of AlphaFold. The main themes that emerged were a lack of access to high-quality training resources and the need for language accessibility through multilingual training, essential for supporting diverse linguistic backgrounds and fostering inclusive engagement. In parallel, addressing infrastructure needs is equally important, including reliable internet connectivity, adequate computing resources, and secure data storage solutions to support both research and training activities effectively.

Fostering a collaborative community that empowers trainers and enables the exchange of best practices to enhance research and learning is also crucial. Addressing these challenges is essential to bridge historical inequities in access to computational structural biology training and enable the use of structural data to drive innovation and discovery in underserved regions and across the global life science research community.

Key insights from discussions

The AlphaFold Education Summit served as a crucial forum to identify key challenges and propose actionable solutions for achieving equitable access to AlphaFold and its associated training. Extensive discussions among a diverse group of participants, including researchers, educators from diverse regions, and representatives from Google DeepMind and EMBL–EBI, yielded valuable insights across several critical areas. It also served to create a network to advance AlphaFold training and accessibility worldwide.

Infrastructure and resources

A prominent and recurring challenge identified was the disparity in access to essential infrastructure in under-resourced regions. This encompassed limited computational capacity for running AlphaFold, often exacerbated by unreliable power supplies and inconsistent low-bandwidth internet connectivity. To address these constraints, participants proposed several strategic interventions: fostering collaborations with cloud computing providers, forming partnerships with High-Performance Computing (HPC) centres or well-resourced institutions, and developing training materials tailored for offline use and low-bandwidth environments. Additionally, the importance of ensuring that hosting institutions are equipped with basic hardware resources, such as laptops or workstations for participants, was also strongly emphasised. A need for a backup power source was also recommended.

Training, expertise and mentorship

A critical barrier identified was the shortage of trainers proficient in AlphaFold and structural bioinformatics, particularly within under-resourced regions, largely due to limited formal training opportunities and a lack of access to structured learning environments. Participants strongly emphasised the need for foundational, high-quality training materials and adaptable curricula tailored to diverse expertise levels and local research contexts. Recommendations included creating training resources suitable for various delivery methods, such as in-person, online, and hybrid formats. Establishment of a repository that aligns with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles, complete with guidelines for curriculum development and contextual

adaptation to cater to interdisciplinary gaps, was proposed to ensure consistency and facilitate scalability.

To address the knowledge gap, the implementation of "Train-the-Trainer" (TtT) programmes was widely supported. These programmes would extend beyond technical instruction to encompass effective andragogical approaches, empowering local experts to deliver high-quality training. Successful initiatives such as the Pan African Bioinformatics Network (H3ABioNet)(10) and the African BioGenome Project (AfricaBP) Open Institute workshops, which provide hands-on training in genomics and bioinformatics across Africa (16), demonstrate the effectiveness of targeted capacity-building efforts in addressing expertise gaps, as evidenced by the emergence of local trainer networks and increased regional course offerings.

The value of mentorship in supporting researchers, particularly those new to the field, was also highlighted. The importance of effective mentor-mentee matching, potentially through a curated list of mentors with specific expertise, was discussed. Innovative approaches such as reverse mentoring and peer mentorship were proposed to foster sustained engagement and knowledge exchange within the community. Furthermore, guidance on identifying and applying for regionally specific funding opportunities and other relevant support resources was recognised as a key to accelerating access to available resources.

Language and inclusivity

Language barriers were consistently identified as a major impediment to equitable access and participation, particularly in regions with rich linguistic diversity where English is not the primary language of research or education. The careful use of AI translation tools for developing training resources in multiple languages, coupled with validation by local experts, was proposed as a vital step towards greater inclusivity. Tailoring training approaches to address these linguistic challenges, including the creation of beginner-friendly materials and readily available technical support during training sessions, was also recommended. Furthermore, participants proposed that offering training content in multiple languages, especially those spoken in low and

middle-income countries, can enhance learner engagement, reduce exclusion, and foster greater adoption across linguistically diverse communities.

Funding and sustainability

Securing adequate and sustained funding for training programmes, essential infrastructure, and long-term community-building initiatives emerged as a major concern, particularly for ensuring continuity and impact beyond short-term projects. Participants emphasised the urgency of exploring collaborative funding models that diversify financial support and strengthen institutional resilience, thereby ensuring the longevity of training efforts. Several approaches were suggested, including forming a consortium of academic institutions to pool resources; cultivating strategic partnerships with industry stakeholders who directly benefit from a skilled workforce in AlphaFold; and computational structural biology, offering mutual value by advancing innovation while supporting workforce development; and engaging philanthropic organisations through collaborative grant applications, drawing inspiration from impactful initiatives funded by Wellcome (e.g., the "Train the Trainer: Design Genomics and Bioinformatics Training" course led by Wellcome Connecting Science) (17) and the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative (CZI) (www.chanzuckerberg.com/).

Integrating AlphaFold training into university curricula or institutional planning presents a viable pathway towards creating self-sustaining models, embedding the training into long-term academic strategies. This can involve several approaches: for undergraduate and master's taught courses, institutions could strategically assess their current structural biology or related curricula to identify areas where incorporating AlphaFold training modules could provide students with early exposure to cutting-edge AI applications in life sciences. Such a proactive approach can enhance students' ability to use AlphaFold effectively, critically assess its outputs, and readily adapt to similar AI-driven tools throughout their careers. For early-stage researchers, such as PhD students and those undertaking master's research projects, dedicated training programmes focused on applying AlphaFold in research contexts can equip them with essential skills, fostering a more proactive engagement with AI-driven research methodologies and potentially leading to more innovative outcomes. Pilot programmes

demonstrating the tangible impact of integrating AI tools like AlphaFold into both teaching and research environments can serve as persuasive case studies to advocate for long-term institutional investment and strategic alignment.

Furthermore, the concept of sub-granting mechanisms was proposed to enhance flexibility in funding allocation and foster collaborative projects across diverse institutions, particularly benefiting those with limited direct access to major funding opportunities. Sub-granting involves larger, well-resourced entities, such as major grant recipients or international research consortia, allocating portions of their funds to smaller institutions or grassroots initiatives. This model enables targeted support for regionally relevant training activities, including workshops, translations, infrastructure set-up, and mentoring. This allows for targeted support of local needs and catalyses grassroots efforts in areas such as the organisation and delivery of training workshops and courses (both in-person and virtual), the development of educational materials, the establishment and maintenance of necessary infrastructure (e.g., teaching labs and online platforms), potential contributions to computational resources in under-resourced settings through collaborations, and the support of community-building activities encompassing online forums, mentorship programmes, and regional networking events.

Developing open-access resource repositories, such as those exemplified by The Carpentries (18), remains a key strategy for maximising the impact of financial investments, avoiding duplication, and enabling rapid localisation and reuse of training content. Alongside this, effective Train-the-Trainer networks, such as H3ABioNet (19), represent powerful models for building sustainable capacity. H3ABioNet's experience demonstrates the importance of adapting training approaches to create a sustainable training environment, particularly in resource-limited settings, by utilising a combination of training modalities, sharing FAIR training materials, and fostering synergistic collaborations.

Geopolitical and logistical challenges

Participants acknowledge that geopolitical challenges and logistical barriers, such as visa and travel restrictions, significantly impede international collaboration and participation in training events. Time zone differences and the often lengthy legal processes associated with international collaborations were also identified as complicating factors. Potential solutions included the establishment of regional training hubs or collaborative clusters to mitigate the impact of geopolitical issues and facilitate cooperation among neighbouring countries. The Africa Biogenome Project Open Institute's emphasis on multi-partner and multi-country frameworks demonstrates the importance of sustained investment and collaboration for effective capacity building (16).

Lack of cross-interdisciplinarity in research environments

In many LMICs, biomedical research is often conducted in isolation, with limited multidisciplinary and minimal cross-disciplinary collaboration. This fragmentation is further exacerbated by academic curricula that insufficiently incorporate interdisciplinary fields such as bioinformatics, computer science, and biophysics. For instance, chemistry-based programmes may lack comprehensive training in biological macromolecular systems, thereby reducing the flexibility and readiness of researchers to engage in collaborative projects. Tools like AlphaFold, which are inherently designed for use by researchers from diverse disciplinary backgrounds, are unlikely to achieve their full potential in such environments. To address this, local training programmes in AlphaFold could be intentionally designed to include participants from a range of scientific backgrounds. Such inclusive training efforts can help foster cross-disciplinary collaboration, mentorship networks, and sustained engagement not only with AlphaFold but also with the broader field of computational structural biology.

Long-term strategies for sustainable training

A strong consensus emerged on the need to cultivate a robust international community to coordinate, sustain, and expand global AlphaFold training capacity. This community would focus on identifying committed host institutions within each participating country and ensuring broad participation and shared responsibility among local stakeholders to enhance the resilience and sustainability of training efforts. The establishment of a

global community of AlphaFold experts, united by shared goals, was proposed as a mechanism to foster collaboration, facilitate knowledge exchange, advocate for increased resources and supportive policies, promote capacity development, provide professional recognition, and ultimately amplify the impact of AlphaFold education and application. Such a community could play a key role in developing standardised training curricula and disseminating best practices. In addition, it could co-develop multilingual, culturally contextualised resources to improve inclusivity and reach in non-English-speaking regions. The community could also curate and maintain an open-access repository of training materials and datasets, case studies, and workflows relevant to various scientific domains. Collectively, these efforts aim to ensure that AlphaFold's benefits are more widely shared and effectively applied across diverse research environments.

To maintain momentum and ensure accountability, a blended approach combining annual global meetings with robust hybrid and virtual components to accommodate diverse geographic, time-zone, and connectivity needs, particularly for those facing travel restrictions, and more frequent regional or local meetings, was strongly encouraged. The development of a dynamic user group to facilitate ongoing information sharing was highlighted as a critical element of sustainable training. Successful models such as the Collaborative Computational Project Number 4 (CCP4) (20) and the Collaborative Computational Project on Electron Microscopy (CCP-EM) bulletin boards have cultivated vibrant communities of researchers in structural biology across experience levels (21), and were cited as valuable examples to emulate.

Participants also emphasised the importance of integrating in-person and virtual training modalities to maximise reach and impact. Furthermore, the need for a dedicated operational organiser, rather than solely relying on scientists with competing research priorities, was considered to be crucial for ensuring the continuity and long-term success of these training initiatives. This could be a part-time, paid role to ensure consistent effort and focus. Establishing regional training clusters and peer-led learning models can also help decentralise delivery and improve sustainability, particularly in areas with limited institutional infrastructure.

Call to action and recommendations

To address the challenges identified during the summit, the following actionable recommendations were proposed. We share these as a blueprint, not only for community-designed and informed initiatives for AlphaFold, but also to help shape the effective adoption of other disruptive technologies for scientists.

Action Area	Recommendations
Resource sharing infrastructure	Create infrastructure for sharing training resources responsibly.
Community engagement & mentorship	Develop a centralised platform for knowledge sharing, mentorship, and community engagement, drawing inspiration from successful models like The Carpentries.
Sustainability & funding	Secure sustainable funding for training programmes, infrastructure, and community-building efforts through diverse collaborative models, such as coalitions of funders and strategic industry partnerships.
	Advocate for the integration of training costs into institutional financial planning, exploring avenues like embedding them within university curricula or departmental budgets to ensure long-term financial support.
	Engage with funding organisations to establish resource-sharing mechanisms, complementing collaborative funding models, to maximise the impact of available funds and minimise redundant resource development.
	Foster partnerships with technology companies, cloud providers, and bioinformatics startups to support resource donation, technical support, and innovation pipelines.
Community building	Organise regional hubs or collaborative clusters to address geopolitical and logistical challenges and foster collaboration both inter-country and among neighbouring countries.

	<p>Establish an international community of experts and regional working groups to coordinate training initiatives, share resources, and foster global knowledge exchange.</p>
	<p>Develop virtual platforms and leverage existing technologies to build and sustain communities, facilitating continuous engagement and resource sharing.</p>
Policy and advocacy	<p>Engage policymakers to raise awareness of inequities in access to computational resources, training, funding, basic infrastructure, and international collaboration.</p>
	<p>Advocate for the integration of AlphaFold and computational structural biology training into university curricula and institutional budgets.</p>
	<p>Develop metrics, case studies, and success stories from diverse contexts to demonstrate the impact of AlphaFold training programmes and highlight the benefits of investing in AlphaFold education.</p>
	<p>Promote interdisciplinary AlphaFold training programmes that engage participants from diverse scientific backgrounds.</p>
Global engagement & networking	<p>Establish an international community to support long-term training initiatives, identifying host institutions and ensuring the involvement of multiple individuals per country.</p>
	<p>Host annual meetings (with strong hybrid and virtual components) and maintain a dedicated online channel to build and sustain a global community for information sharing, collaboration, and ongoing engagement.</p>
Training & expertise development	<p>Implement effective mentorship programmes, including strategies for matching mentors and mentees and fostering peer mentorship.</p>
	<p>Implement comprehensive "Train-the-Trainer" (TtT) programmes to build a global network of endorsed AlphaFold trainers, focusing on both technical proficiency and pedagogical skills.</p>

Conclusion

The AlphaFold Education Summit provided a valuable platform to identify critical needs and opportunities for broadening access to AlphaFold and empowering researchers globally, particularly in LMICs. The discussions and proposed solutions underscore a collective desire to facilitate the effective integration of AlphaFold into research, thereby accelerating scientific discovery worldwide.

The insights gained from the summit now pave the way for more effective, community-led, and informed approaches to AlphaFold training and adoption. Paramount among these is the development of a comprehensive global Train-the-Trainer programme tailored to local contexts, aiming to cultivate self-sufficient expertise. Simultaneously, fostering interdisciplinary collaborations, informed by the specific needs articulated by the community, will be crucial to unlock AlphaFold's potential across varied scientific fields, especially in addressing challenges relevant to LMICs. The implementation of accessible local workshops and the development of user-friendly resources, guided by the expressed needs of under-resourced regions, are vital for enhancing adoption and lowering barriers to access. By prioritising inclusivity, long-term sustainability, and collaborative partnerships informed by the community, we can enhance the capacity of researchers across the globe to harness AlphaFold's capabilities and those of other emerging AI tools.

This community-driven approach holds the potential to accelerate scientific progress in low-resource research settings, broadening opportunities for researchers who may lack access to expensive experimental equipment. Community-informed training approaches, combined with open-access tools and multilingual resources, will be vital for enabling a global constellation of research teams to integrate AlphaFold into their scientific workflows. Moving forward, a continued focus on these learnings will be essential to ensure that the integration of AI-informed tools like AlphaFold effectively benefits the global scientific community, fostering profound advantages of discovery that are shared and contribute to a more just and prosperous future.

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